

Investigation of bone conduction stimulation efficiency on the skull surface and below assessed by cochlear promontory vibration

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Stimulation sites closer to the cochlea result in higher output for bone conduction devices (BCD), increasing maximum output and reducing energy consumption. In our study, alternative coupling sites closer to the ear canal (EC), in cortical and spongy bone, were investigated and the influence on ipsi- and contralateral bone conduction output was quantified.

Methods: Cochlear promontory (CP) vibrations were measured by 1D laser Doppler vibrometry, using five freshly frozen (10 ears) whole human cadaver heads. A percutaneous actuator was implanted at different positions: five on the surface 25 to 55 mm posterior to the EC and two recessed positions 20 mm posterior to the EC at 5 to 8 mm depth. Stimulation was performed using a stepped sine, consisting of 78 frequencies from 0.1 to 10 kHz.

Results: In comparison to positions 50–55 mm to the EC, average CP vibrations showed significantly increased CP vibrations, ranging from 6.5 dB to 13.9 dB between 0.5 and 4 kHz at closer and recessed positions. In contrast, contralateral results showed smaller output amplitudes ($0.5 \text{ kHz} < f < 4 \text{ kHz}$). For positions closer to the EC, transcranial attenuation was considerably increased up to 25.2 dB at 4 kHz.

Conclusion: Our results show a significant increase of CP vibrations in stimulation direction, for positions closer to the cochlea. Moreover, the feasibility of bone anchors in spongy bone was demonstrated, leading to similar output when compared to positions on the skull surface.

1. Introduction

Bone conduction devices (BCDs) offer alternative auditory rehabilitation options for individuals with conductive (CHL) and mixed hearing loss (MHL), in case middle ear reconstructive surgeries and conventional hearing aids pose no option (Beros et al., 2022; Maier et al., 2022). By utilizing different independent BC pathways (Surendran and Stenfelt, 2022), BCDs bypass external/middle ear pathologies, delivering sound by bone vibration to both cochleae. BCDs represent a pivotal advancement in otological treatment, enhancing communication and quality of life (Hua and Lewis, 2024). To date, there are several devices on the market and more under development, e.g., the Bonebridge (MED-EL GmbH, Austria), the Sentio TI (Oticon Medical, Sweden), the Ponto (Oticon Medical, Sweden), the Cochlear™ Baha® (Cochlear Ltd.,

Australia) and the Cochlear™ Osia® (Cochlear Ltd., Australia). These BCDs are divided into transcutaneous bone conduction devices (TBCDs) which are semi-implantable active implants (Bonebridge, Sentio TI and Osia®) and percutaneous bone conduction devices (PBCDs) which are based on an active transducer, mounted onto a skin-penetrating abutment and a passive implant fixated in the bone (Ponto, Baha®). (Ellsperman et al., 2021) Furthermore, the development of these BCDs resulted in different ways of bone-implant-interface: a single contact point via implant (Ponto, Baha® and Osia®), fixation by two cortical bone screws (Bonebridge) or a planar contact (Sentio TI) (Ellsperman et al., 2021; Ghoncheh et al., 2022).

Understanding the efficiency of BCDs across diverse stimulation sites is essential for advancing the design and efficacy of auditory prosthetic systems. In the past two decades, studies have reported increased

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stimulation efficiency for bone conduction sites positioned closer to the cochlea. (Stenfelt and Goode, 2005; Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2008; Håkansson et al., 2008) These studies explored the hypothesis that optimizing bone conduction stimulation sites could enhance device output to the cochlea. Researchers measured cochlear promontory (CP) vibrations by using 1D and 3D Laser Doppler vibrometry (LDV) or 3D accelerometry as a proxy for perceived loudness. Additionally, intra-cochlear pressure differences (ICPD) were examined as a more direct indicator of auditory perception. (Dobrev et al., 2022; Fierens et al., 2022, 2023; Felix et al., 2023; Wils et al., 2024). Another study (Felix et al., 2023) also investigated the potential for achieving closer proximity to the cochlea by applying stimulation directly on the semicircular canals (SSC) and at a position near the cochlea. The general trend in these study results indicate an improved output closer to the cochlea, suggesting that transcutaneous devices that have fewer positioning restrictions, likely can be used to increase output.

The objective of this study was to determine the efficiency of single point stimulation at various positions on the skull surface as well as at recessed stimulation sites below the skull surface. Thus, investigating the effect of proximity to the cochlea in cortical bone and stimulation in spongy bone by measuring CP vibrations on both sides in human cadaveric heads.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Specimen preparation

This study was conducted, using five freshly frozen male cadaver heads (10 ears) under approval of the ethics committee (EC) of the Hannover Medical School (10658_BO_K_2022). The cadaver heads were defrosted over the course of 72 h prior to the experiments; 48 h at 4 °C and 24 h at room temperature. Cone Beam Computer Tomography (CBCT) data were used to identify possible skull fractures and verify eligibility for the experiments, as assessed by an experienced surgeon. To account for the loss of central spinal fluid (CSF), cadaver heads were refilled with 1.2 wt% agar solution (Grosshörmichen et al., 2016), through an opening at the sagittal suture approximately above the *foramen magnum*. To expose the region of interest on the temporal and parietal bone, three incisions were made and the skin retracted. Access to the cochlear promontory (CP) was obtained through a triangular incision (approx. 2 × 2 × 4 mm) in the tympanic membrane, between six

and seven o'clock on the left side and five and six o'clock on the right side. For subsequent measurements, a reflector pad of approximately 1 mm² was placed on each CP.

2.2. Positions, conditions and test sequence

Ipsi- and contralateral CP vibrations in medial – lateral direction were measured by 1D LDV through the external ear canal (EAC). For this study, seven stimulation sites relative to the EAC had been identified (five on the skull surface and two 5 mm recessed): Reference 1 (R1), Reference 2 (R2), Closer 1 (C1), Closer 2 (C2), Closer 3 (C3), Deeper 1 (D1) and Deeper 2 (D2) (see Fig. 1a & b). In experiments, positions were marked using a template similar to the schematic in Fig. 1c.

The two reference positions R1 and R2 were chosen as estimates for commonly used implantation sites of transcutaneous and percutaneous bone conduction devices, at distances of 55 (R1) and 53 mm (R2) from the EAC. (Fierens et al., 2022) Positions C1 to 3 were located at different angles (40°, 72° and 132°; from top to bottom) relative to the anterior-posterior direction with distances of 25 (C1 and C2) and 30 mm (C3) from the EAC (see Fig. 1c). At 20 mm, the positions D1 (96°) and D2 (72°) were the closest to the EAC and cochlea in this study, with the top rim of each implant placed approximately 5 mm below the skull surface (see Fig. 1b). For stimulation, an electrically contacted Cochlear™ Baha® 5 actuator (Cochlear Ltd., Australia) without housing was used. Cochlear™ Baha® BI300 implants (4 mm; Cochlear Ltd., Australia) were placed according to the Cochlear™ Physicians Guide and Cochlear™ and Baha® BA400 Dermalock abutments (12 mm; Cochlear Ltd., Australia) were screwed onto each BI300, for all positions. Since the BI300 is designed to be implanted in cortical bone, Paladur® (Kulzer, Germany) was used to create an interface between the implant and the spongy bone at the recessed implantation sites D1 and D2. At these locations, residual moisture on the bone surface was removed using superglue (UHU GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) and activator spray (Conrad Electronic SE, Germany) in the first step. In the second step, the core holes were filled with Paladur® and the implants placed into them, with a curing time of 10–15 min. This resulted in an estimated interface of approx. 1 mm thickness around the BI300 with additional Paladur®-migration into adjacent air cells. The rim of each implant was kept clean from cement, to ensure a proper connection between BI300 and abutment.

For the LDV measurements, heads were placed on a silicone

Fig. 1. Overview of the stimulation positions. (a) Cadaver head with implants and abutments at surface positions R1, R2, C1, C2, C3; (b) recessed implant positions at D1 and D2. (c) Schematics of a skull with the distances relative to the EAC and angles of the individual positions relative to the cranial-caudal-axis in the sagittal plane.

elastomer head holder, with the sagittal plane parallel to the table. Measurements were performed on two consecutive days. First day: stimulation at positions R1, R2, C1, C2 and C3 on side A. Second day: D1 and D2 on side A as well as R1, R2, C1, C2, C3, D1 and D2 on side B. Recordings of responses to all stimulations were performed on the ipsi- and contralateral CP. Heads were stored in a cooling room at 4 °C overnight.

2.3. Stimulation setup and procedure

Cochlear™ Baha® 5 actuators, modified to enable direct electrical input, were used to provide the stimulation. The electrical contacts were glued to the actuators body, to reduce tension on the compliant cables. To protect the actuators from moisture and body fluids, the cap of a latex glove finger was used as a splash guard. The input voltage was chosen as 2 V_{pp}, resulting in an output force level matching acoustic stimulation at 90 dB SPL with a commercial Cochlear™ Baha® 5 Sound Processor. For signal generation and recording a data acquisition device (NI-4431 BNC; National Instruments, USA) with a 24-bit analogue-to-digital converter was used in combination with a custom tailored LabVIEW (National Instruments, USA) program (Ghoncheh et al., 2022). A stepped sine consisting of 78 logarithmically spaced frequencies, ranging from 0.1 to 10 kHz, was supplied via a buffer amplifier (SA2, Tucker-Davis Technologies, USA) to the actuator. The data acquisition was conducted with a sampling rate of 51.2 kS/s and the noise floor was estimated, based on the average of 5 frequency bins below and 5 above the stimulus frequency. Responses were averaged, until a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 12 dB was achieved, for a minimum of 30 and up to a maximum of 1000 samples. All data below the SNR of 12 dB were excluded from the following analysis.

2.4. Reference measurements and linear compensation

To test reproducible performance of the actuators, skull simulator measurements (TU 1000, Nobelpharma, Sweden) were carried out before and after each experimental day. Three different Cochlear™ Baha® 5 actuators were used during the experiments. To account for differences in actuator-performance and to reduce the resulting systematic error, measurement results were normalized to a “standard actuator” resulting from the frequency-dependent average over all pre-experimental skull simulator measurements (see Fig. 2). The comparison with Baha 5 OVFL90 data (maximum output force level at 90 dB SPL) from the data sheet, shows similar results with a slight shift of the resonance frequency and maximum in output force level. In contrast to

Fig. 2. Average skull simulator measurement ($n = 10$) across all daily pre-experimental measurements (solid orange line), minimum and maximum (black dashed lines) as well as OVFL90 data from data sheet (solid blue line).

the electrically contacted Baha 5 actuators used in this study, the sound processor driven Baha 5 shows a significant decrease in output force level above 6 kHz due to the cut-off frequency of the processor (see Fig. 2).

2.5. Data acquisition setup and 1 dimensional laser doppler vibrometry

Ipsi- and contralateral CP velocities were measured, using a 1D LDV (OFV 5000; Polytec GmbH, Germany) with a micromanipulator (MM3; Polytec GmbH, Germany) mounted to a surgical microscope (OPMI 1, Carl Zeiss AG, Germany) using a sensitivity of 5 mm/s/V. The middle ear was visually accessed through the prepared triangular incisions in the tympanic membrane and the CP vibration measured in the direction of the EAC (medial-lateral).

2.6. Statistical analysis

Data collected from the measures of the five heads were normalized to the mean actuator performance (see Fig. 2) and pooled as frequency dependent data sets. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to test for normal distribution ($0.01 < p \leq 0.05$). A paired t -test was used to determine statistically significant differences between CP velocities at each frequency. For all significance levels ($0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$) a power of 0.8 was defined as additional requirement, to enhance the robustness of the results. Data visualization and analysis were performed using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, USA) and OriginPro 2023b (OriginLab Corporation, USA).

3. Results

Due to an underperformance of the initially used actuator, detected in the post-experimental skull simulator measurement, one complete data set had to be excluded from the analysis. Thus, the overall sample size for the ipsilateral measurements resulted in $n = 10$ ears and for the contralateral side in $n = 9$ ears. The Shapiro-Wilk tests performed confirmed that the datasets were normally distributed.

R1 vs R2: The ipsi- and contralateral CP velocities are shown in Fig. 3. The comparison of the ipsilateral measurements in Fig. 3A, shows highly similar results for frequencies up to 4 kHz and minor differences above 4 kHz. The average standard deviation was 4.7 dB for both data sets (R1 and R2) across all frequencies with rare statistically significant differences (between R1 and R2) of the population means at 5.875 kHz and 8.95 kHz.

Fig. 3B depicts the corresponding results for the contralateral measurements with statistically significant differences of the population means up to 0.625 kHz and around 6 kHz. Contralateral measurements showed slightly greater differences between the population means, while the average standard deviations across all frequencies remained similar (4.94 dB for R1 and 4.81 dB for R2).

Due to the lack of statistically significant differences between the two reference positions and the availability of corresponding values in dB SPL (Carlsson et al., 1995; Carlsson and Hakansson, 1997), R1 was chosen as reference for the following comparisons.

R1 vs C1 vs C2 vs C3: To investigate the influence of stimulation site proximity to the cochlear on CP vibrations, three closer positions (see Fig. 1) were investigated. Fig. 4 shows the results for ipsi- and contralateral measurements at closer positions in comparison to R1. Average differences were calculated for each frequency and additionally the average over all frequencies between 0.5 and 4 kHz.

The ipsilateral comparison for C1 displays a difference of 9.4 dB on average as well as a maximum difference of 15.0 dB at 3 kHz. Highly significant differences to R1 were found at most frequencies above 0.675 kHz (see Fig. 4A). The average difference on the contralateral side was 2.5 dB with a maximum of 7.3 dB at 4 kHz (see Fig. 4B) and exhibited fewer statistically significant differences, primarily in the low to mid-frequency range (up to 2 kHz).

Fig. 3. (A) Ipsilateral ($n = 10$) and (B) contralateral ($n = 9$) average CP velocity for R1 (solid orange line) and R2 (solid blue line) with standard deviation in corresponding colors. Statistically significant differences are indicated by the symbols at the top: white triangles for $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, dark grey triangles for $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$ and black triangles for $p \leq 0.001$.

Fig. 4. Ipsilateral ($n = 10$) and contralateral ($n = 9$) CP velocity for R1 (solid orange line) vs closer positions (solid blue lines), with standard deviations in corresponding colors. Statistically significant differences between the compared positions are indicated by the symbols at the top: white triangles for $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, dark grey triangles for $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$ and black triangles for $p \leq 0.001$.

The ipsi- and contralateral results for C2 and R1 in comparison, are shown in Fig. 4C & D, with a maximum difference of 18.3 dB at 3 kHz and 13.9 dB on average for the ipsilateral side. Thus, displaying the highest mean and maximum difference in all data sets. However, C2 showed the highest standard deviation for all ipsilateral measurements. Highly significant differences were identified for most of the frequencies in the mid-range between 0.6 to 4 kHz. The contralateral results showed significantly fewer statistically significant differences, primarily between 0.8 kHz and 2.2 kHz. Additionally, the comparison of C2 and R1 on the contralateral side showed an average difference of 3.7 dB as well as a maximum difference of 10.1 dB (4 kHz).

The ipsilateral results for C3 were on average 6.5 dB higher than for the R1 position with a maximum of 13.4 dB at 3 kHz (see Fig. 4E). Statistical analysis showed highly significant differences for six investigated frequencies below 4 kHz. The comparison of R1 and C3 on the contralateral side resulted in 0.9 dB difference on average, a maximum of 7.3 dB at 4 kHz as well as few significant differences at 1, 1.087 and 1.175 kHz.

C1 vs D1 vs D2: To assess both the impact of proximity to the EAC and anchoring sites beneath the skull surface, two deeper positions (approximately 5 mm below the surface) were examined. Fig. 5A to D show the results for ipsi- and contralateral measurements at positions D1 and D2 in comparison to C1.

C1 was located at a distance of 25 mm to the EAC and D1 at 20 mm with a depth of approx. 5 mm (see Fig. 1b). In comparison, the ipsilateral results displayed a difference of 3.7 dB on average and a maximum difference of 6.3 dB (1.767 kHz). Statistically significant differences occurred in 20 out of 41 frequencies between 0.5 kHz and 4 kHz. No statistically significant differences were observed on the contralateral side. The contralateral comparison resulted in a difference of 1.9 dB on average and a local maximum difference of 6.4 dB at 2.9 kHz (absolute maximum of 7.9 dB at 10 kHz).

The ipsilateral results for D2 (20 mm distance to the EAC, approx. 5

mm depth) were 2.7 dB higher on average than for the C1 position with a local maximum of 5.1 dB at 1.788 kHz and an absolute maximum of 5.5 dB at 4.625 kHz.

Significant differences were observed in 11 of the 41 frequencies tested between 0.5 kHz and 4 kHz. The comparison on the contralateral side resulted in 1.3 dB difference on average and a local maximum 5 dB at 2.863 kHz (absolute maximum of 5.9 dB at 10 kHz). There were no statistically significant differences found on the contralateral side (see Fig. 5B & D).

3.1. Transcranial attenuation

Based on the results for the ipsi- and contralateral measurements, the transcranial attenuation (TA), defined as ipsilateral CP velocity minus the contralateral CP velocity, was determined. Fig. 6A shows the results for each stimulation site and Fig. 6B to D the direct comparison of C1 vs C2, C1 vs D2 and D1 vs D2. All differences between positions were frequency-dependently calculated for each ear individually and the averages across all frequencies between 0.1 and 10 kHz for each comparison.

The average TAs for all positions were below 0 dB at frequencies < 0.375 kHz and displayed an absolute minimum of -6.5 dB at 0.45 kHz (C1). R1 displays an average TA of -0.7 dB for frequencies below and 4.9 dB above 2 kHz (1.9 dB overall) with an absolute maximum of 10.4 dB at 6.812 kHz. For frequencies above 0.375 kHz the remaining TAs (all closer and deeper positions) increased on average until 0.787 kHz and after a short decrease, increased again for frequencies > 1.35 kHz. Closer positions displayed a mean TA between 12.8 and 16.1 dB for frequencies > 1.35 kHz as well as absolute maxima of 22.2 dB at 8 kHz (C1), 25.2 dB at 4 kHz (C2) and 20.6 dB at 6.187 kHz (C3). For the deeper positions, the mean TAs were located around 16.4 dB and the absolute maxima of 25.7 dB at 10 kHz (D1) and 25.3 dB at 8.95 kHz (D2).

The results for C2 are 2.2 dB higher on average than for the C1

Fig. 5. Ipsilateral ($n = 10$) and contralateral ($n = 9$) CP velocity for C1 (solid orange line) vs deeper positions (solid blue line), with standard deviations in corresponding colors. Statistically significant differences between the compared positions are indicated by the symbols at the top: white triangles for $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, dark grey triangles for $0.001 < p \leq 0.01$ and black triangles for $p \leq 0.001$.

Fig. 6. Averaged TA ($n = 9$) (A) R1 (solid orange line), closer (blue lines) and deeper (black lines) positions, (B) C1 (orange solid line) versus C2 (blue solid line), (C) C1 (orange solid line) versus D2 (blue solid line) and (D) D1 (orange solid line) versus D2 (blue solid line). Shaded areas of corresponding colors depict standard deviations.

position with a maximum of 9.6 dB at 0.45 kHz. In comparison, the TA results of C1 vs D2 display a mean difference of 1.3 dB and a maximum difference of 6.9 dB (8.95 kHz). The comparison of D1 and D2 shows an average difference of 0.5 dB with a maximum of 4.9 dB at 8 kHz.

4. Discussion

4.1. Ipsi- and contralateral CP vibrations

In this study, CP vibrations were measured at seven different positions in human cadaver heads. This included two reference positions (R1 and R2), three closer positions (C1, C2 and C3) as well as two deeper positions (D1 and D2), to investigate the influence of stimulation site proximity to the EAC and cochlea on the output performance of BC devices. The responses for both reference positions were similar with no major significant differences (except for two frequencies > 5 kHz). On the contralateral side, a few but minor significant differences were observed below 0.7 kHz as well as around 6 kHz (see Fig. 3). In contrast, the comparison of all three closer positions clearly showed a pronounced effect of proximity to the cochlea on the ipsilaterally measured promontory velocities, with significantly increased responses compared to R1 at higher frequencies (see Fig. 4). A gradient from cranial (parietal) to caudal (mastoid) was observed, with the highest CP velocity levels at the mastoidal tip (C2). The data analysis also showed a high homogeneity of results i.e. a low overall inter-sample standard deviations of < 5 dB on average for all specimens. The realignment of the LDV system between measurements and sessions could potentially introduce a confounding factor. However, as the measurement along the EAC limits the access angle to $< 5^\circ$, this was assumed to be of minor importance compared to the anatomical variations between samples.

Our results show that stimulation positions closer to the cochlea result in generally higher CP vibrations on the ipsilateral side. Stenfelt and Goode et al. 2005 (accelerometry and LDV, mini-transducer) and

Eeg-Olofsson et al. 2008 (LDV, Baha® transducer) reported increased ipsilateral responses of approx. 7 and up to 13 dB, respectively for positions comparable to R1 and C1 (maximum of 15 dB in this study). For positions similar to R1 and C2, but with a planar surface actuator, Ghoncheh et al. 2022 (LDV, Sentio TI and Ponto) described increased CP velocity levels of up to 13 dB (maximum of 18.3 dB in this study). Therefore, the results of this study are qualitatively in line with the findings of Ghoncheh et al., but with overall higher magnitude. Håkansson et al. 2008 investigated the direct comparison between a Classic-300 percutaneous BAHA (Cochlear Ltd., Australia) at a position 55 mm posterior to the EAC (pos. A, R1 in this study) and a transcutaneous bone conduction implant prototype at a depth of 15 mm in the temporal bone (pos. B). Håkansson et al. reported approx. 10 dB higher ipsilateral promontory acceleration levels, for the same input voltage, at pos. B for frequencies > 0.7 kHz.

The comparison between R1 and all closer positions (C1, C2, C3 ipsilateral) resulted in significantly higher CP vibrations; with the comparison of individual frequencies resulting in even higher differences. According to hypotheses in literature, these high differences can be explained by an underestimation of the reference position R1 in the context of 1D LDV (in medial-lateral direction). (Dobrev et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2021, 2022; Ghoncheh et al., 2022) But not only the measurement method or the magnitude of the vibrational components have a great impact on the results, but also factors like state of defrosting, embalming and preparation method, content of the skull vault or mechanical fixation of the cadaver (Dobrev et al., 2018, 2022; Graf et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the results from this study are in line with previously reported results, even though different actuators, types of attachment, driving method or stimulation positions were used. (Stenfelt and Goode, 2005; Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2013; Beros et al., 2022; Dobrev et al., 2022; Fierens et al., 2022; Ghoncheh et al., 2022; Felix et al., 2023; Wils et al., 2024).

The direct comparison of D1 and D2 with the closest position in the

vicinity (C1) showed less distinct significant differences (see Fig. 5A & C), which are limited to the ipsilateral measurements (see Fig. 5B & D). Talon et al. 2023 investigated the effect of bone density on CP acceleration for stimulation via BCDs, based on the computed bone column density index (CODI in $\text{mg}_{\text{HA}}/\text{mm}^2$). The article states an increased CP acceleration of approx. 6 dB (CODI_{min} vs CODI_{max}) as well as a distinct impact of distance to the cochlea on the transmission (approx. 2 dB/cm). The influence of the bone density was especially pronounced for the 1 and 2 kHz octave bands. D1 and D2 are positioned in mastoidal spongy bone (see Fig. 1b), which shows significantly lower bone density as well as bigger air cells. According to the findings of Talon et al. 2023, this would lead to lower results in comparison to positions in cortical, or generally denser bone (i.e. C1). The implementation of an adequate implant-bone interface for the transmission of vibration in spongy bone was another aim of this investigation. Which has been achieved by using the cement Paladur®, a commercially available material limited to experimental use. The results for these deeper positions showed at least similar CP vibrations compared to sites on the skull surface. Similar to Talon et al., the most significant differences were observed between 0.7 and 2 kHz. Furthermore, Talon et al. hypothesized, that the higher the CODI at the implantation site, the higher the stiffness of the interface and the better the transmission of vibration. Based on this, the interface created in spongy bone is presumably comparable to an implant in cortical bone. (Talon et al., 2023) However, a tight connection in porous bone can be potentially achieved with another possible biocompatible method for fixation in non-cortical bone: bone welding. This method utilizes ultrasound to fuse the implant material with the surrounding bone. Previous results showed neither alterations, thermally induced damages, significant foreign body reactions nor fibrous tissue. (Mai et al., 2007)

4.2. 1D LDV vs 3D as proxy for hearing perception

Cochlear promontory motion is widely used as an estimate for BC hearing sensation in cadaver experiments (Stenfelt and Goode, 2005; Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2013; Dobrev et al., 2019; Beros et al., 2022; Fierens et al., 2022; Felix et al., 2023; Wils et al., 2024). Due to its comparably simple handling and the accessibility of the CP through the EAC without a posterior tympanotomy, 1D LDV is the primarily used measurement method. Literature reported sufficient correlation between average CP motion and average BC thresholds (Stump et al., 2018; Felix et al., 2023) of less than 2 dB differences (Stenfelt and Goode, 2005). However, 1D LDV is a proxy and may be subject to inaccuracies, in case different actuator types or locations of stimulation are investigated. Additionally, linear regression analysis with R^2 of up to 0.93, with a root mean square error (RMSE) of 1.94 dB, was reported for CP vibrations and ICPDs for stimulation at the percutaneous BCD standard position corresponding to our position R1 (Wils et al., 2024). Apparently, these results occur predominantly for 1D LDV measurements in direction of the BC stimulation (perpendicular to the skull surface) (Stenfelt, 2012; Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2013; Dobrev et al., 2019, 2022; Wils et al., 2024). Moreover, LDV measurements are usually dominated by pronounced individual differences and merely trends on averages are reported. For frequency-wise comparisons, the deviations commonly exceed the test-retest reliability for pure-tone audiometry, leading to less reliable results (Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2013; Wils et al., 2024). Thus, leading to the hypothesis that a general prediction of hearing sensation is possible, but the predictive power for individual cases is significantly lower (Eeg-Olofsson et al., 2013). These contradicting results could be explained by the numerous influencing factors: bone density at the stimulation site, anatomical structures (skull lines etc.), content of the skull vault, type of bone (cortical or spongy) in the region of implantation, spatial components of the actual stimulation and bone conduction pathways. (Stenfelt and Goode, 2005; Dobrev et al., 2018, 2019, 2022; Talon et al., 2023; Wils et al., 2024) Therefore, measurement methods that collect data across three dimensions, like 3D

accelerometry or 3D LDV, are a potentially more accurate proxy for the human hearing perception. Especially with regards to off-axis vibrations and stimulation position dependent changes in vibration excitation. (Dobrev et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2021, 2022; Ghoncheh et al., 2022) Despite all three dimensions of the stimulation being taken into account, these methods are still only proxies. In preclinical experiments, ICPD measurements promise to reflect perceived loudness more realistically as the physiological phenomenon of pressure difference over the basilar membrane is measured. Even though ICPDs are closer to the ground truth, given by behavioral patient feedback, they may be subject to vibrational artifacts (Felix et al., 2023). Nevertheless, these methods require more extended access to the measured site requiring far more preparation and, in some cases, extensive bone removal (e.g., mastoidectomy), which could also have a huge impact on the results (Dobrev et al., 2018; Ghoncheh et al., 2022). Further investigations into an adequate proxy for human hearing perception in lab experiments should be carried out in future experiments.

4.3. Transcranial attenuation

In this study, the TA was calculated as ipsilateral CP velocity minus contralateral CP velocity levels, with positive values indicating a higher output on the ipsilateral than the contralateral side. In general, TAs for all positions were close to or slightly negative for frequencies < 0.25 kHz and decreased to an absolute minimum at 0.45 kHz (-6.5 dB for C1), which was previously hypothesized to be caused by antiresonance of the skull in that frequency range (Rigato et al., 2019). No distinct differences between closer and deeper positions were observed, but these results showed prominent differences above 0.5 kHz for all positions compared to R1.

These findings align with previously published results from studies involving patients (Stenfelt, 2012; Beros et al., 2022) and cadaver experiments (Dobrev et al., 2019; Beros et al., 2022; Ghoncheh et al., 2022). Stenfelt included 28 single-sided deafness (SSD) patients without a BCD and obtained TA data for a standard bone conduction hearing aid (BCHA) position (comparable to R1) and the typical audiometric position for a BC transducer (Radioear B71) corresponding approximately to C1. Despite the large inter-subject variability in this experiment, a similar trend for the higher frequencies could be observed; with the highest median TA of 9.5 dB (audiometric position) and 7 dB (BCHA position) at 4.49 kHz. Beros et al. reported results from the direct comparison of a mixed patient group (seven SSD patients fitted with Baha 5 Connect and fifteen SSD patients without a BCD) with 3D LDV measurements in five Thiel-embalmed cadaver heads. Data sets showed a similar trend in cadaver specimens and patients, i.e. increasing TA with increasing frequencies, but with 10 dB lower attenuation in the embalmed samples. The average TA, in cadaver heads at a position comparable to R1, was negative for $f < 0.75$ kHz and at an overall maximum of around 12 dB at 3 kHz. Results from the patient group showed an average TA < 0 for all frequencies below 2 kHz and a maximum of around 13 dB at 4 kHz. Similarly, Dobrev et al. reported 3D LDV measurements in five Thiel-embalmed cadaveric specimens with the use of a Baha Cordelle II actuator. The calculated combined CP motion at the “classic BAHA position” (comparable to R1), indicated a TA between -1.5 and -4.5 dB below 0.6 kHz as well as 1 to 12 dB at higher frequencies. Dobrev et al. hypothesized, that magnitude and spatial composition of the vibration is changed by the TA above 0.5 kHz, with an overestimation below 0.5 kHz. Ghoncheh et al. reported results from 1D LDV measurements in five fresh frozen cadaver heads with stimulation via Sentio TI (TCBD) and Ponto (PBCD) actuators at position A (comparable to R1) and B (approx. C2). Similar trends were observed for both actuator types, with TAs below 0 for $f < 1.5$ kHz at pos. A and $f < 0.5$ kHz at pos. B. The highest magnitudes were reached around 23 dB at approx. 5 kHz (PBCD) and approx. 6 kHz (TCBD), with overall 5 to 15 dB higher results for pos. B compared to pos. A.

As previously reported, an increased TA at higher frequencies can be

beneficial for binaural stimulation by BC, due to higher interaural separation (Rigato et al., 2019; Denanto et al., 2022; Ghoncheh et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2023). Our data showed, that positions closer to the EAC result in an approximately 15 to 20 dB higher TA at frequencies > 2.5 kHz, compared to the reference position R1. Lower contralateral masking levels being required in the clinical context, would be an additional practical benefit (Ghoncheh et al., 2022).

5. Conclusion

The presented data indicates that a stimulation closer (all five positions) to the EAC leads to higher cochlear promontory vibration levels, compared to the reference positions at approximately 50–55 mm distance superior-posterior to the ear canal. Stimulation below the skull surface (deeper positions), in spongy bone and closer to the cochlea, shows similar CP vibration levels than positions on the surface. Therefore, this study provides initial evidence of an adequate bone-implant-interface, for achieving comparable results to stimulation on the skull surface. The resulting TA increased notably for positions closer to the EAC, while no distinct differences between closer and deeper positions were found. To transfer the findings of lab experiments to the surgical and audiological reality in clinics, further investigation into adequate proxy measures for human hearing perception or clinical determination of output should be commenced.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alexander du Puits: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kristian Åsnes:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Thomas Lenarz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Hannes Maier:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None declared.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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